

Development of a Talent Management Model for Retention of Junior Commissioned Officers in the Namibian Defence Force

Thaddeus Mumba Mahela

Associate Dean School of Military Science, University of Namibia

Author Email: mmahela@unam.na

Abstract— The purpose of this study was to develop a talent management model for retaining Junior Commissioned Officers (JCOs) in the Namibian Defence Force (NDF). The article provides an overview of the Namibian Defence Force which is comprised of the Namibian army, air force, navy and the military school. A literature review of the various military talent management models are discussed. These models focuses on the talent recruitment, retention and turnover. The proposed talent management model focuses on the job-pursuit intentions of JCOs, which are positively influenced by gender, military rank, military unit and location of the unit. The management implications for this framework are based on how fair Human Resources Management (HRM) practices are perceived within the NDF and this should be supported by constantly reviewing and updating HRM policies and procedures used in the recruitment, promotion and retention of JCOs in the NDF.

Keywords: Talent management, recruitment, retention, turnover, Namibia Defence Force, Junior Commissioned Officers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Staff retention is one of the most daunting issues that military organisations around the world are dealing with, and this has been exacerbated by globalisation, which has increased competitiveness and increased the mobility of highly skilled workers (Mapolisa (2015)). The difficulties of not attracting the right enlistees arises for many reasons, for example, demographic patterns and unclear human resource policies – such as the NDF blanket recruitment of all applicants, which makes it unattractive for university graduates versus secondary-school leavers. The NDF needs to train more naval-weapons technicians, communicators, sensor and electronic operators, and engineers (MoD, 2007). Although some jobs have exceeded their recruitment requirements, the NDF can accept recruitment for excessive occupations at the expense of understaffed persons due to the limit on staff numbers and the limited number of qualified recruits. In the Namibian military, JCOs are those with ranks from Lieutenant to Captain and they therefore form part of the skilled manpower component of the NDF. These officers are of critical importance because they supervise, manage and train soldiers on a daily basis. Solutions that improve the performance of these officers ultimately affects the readiness and capabilities of all NDF units.

II. AN OVERVIEW OF THE NAMIBIAN DEFENCE FORCE

The Namibia Defence Force (NDF) derives its authority for human resource management from several legal frameworks, including the Namibian Constitution (1990), the Namibian Defence Act (Act No. 1 of 2002), and the NDF Military Discipline Code (1992) as outlined in Act 13 (1995). These legal instruments lay the groundwork for effective public service management, overseeing aspects such as employment conditions, discipline, retirement, and the termination of staff members, along with related issues. Additionally, relevant NDF policies encompass the revised Ministry of Defence personnel policies (2007), the Namibia Statement on Defence Policy (1993), the NDF Operational Training Doctrine/Training for War (1995), and the updated salary grading system from 2013. Collectively, these policies provide the framework and procedures governing the terms and conditions of service, which include recruitment criteria, training and education, promotion, appointment, compensation, and retirement for military personnel.

NDF human capital encompasses personnel engaged at every level in the planning, execution, and support of military operations across land, air, and maritime domains. Its main role involves monitoring enemy forces, alongside delivering comprehensive telecommunication services and electronic warfare capabilities to facilitate this task. This includes the planning, development, and implementation of training programs to equip members for their primary responsibilities, as well as strategizing for the enhancement, disposal, and maintenance of weaponry and equipment to ensure optimal resources are available for executing these essential functions (MoD, 2013).

The Namibian Defence Force (NDF) is structured into three branches: the Namibian Army, the Namibian Air Force, and the Namibian Navy. It is important to note that the establishment of the Namibian Army progressed more rapidly than the other two branches. The initial units of the Army were deployed as early as 1990. The Army was established following Namibia's independence, when two former adversaries, the South West Africa Territorial Force (SWATF) and the People's Liberation Army of Namibia (PLAN), were integrated into the newly formed NDF.

II.I. THE NAMIBIAN ARMY

The MoD stipulates its Army policy as follows:

'The Army's principal roles will continue to be as already outlined in the defence policy. The Army will strive to maximise its operational effectiveness through the recruitment of the best young men and women who wish to pursue a military career, their effective training and employment. The Army's equipment priorities are improved troop-lift capacity (road and air); engineer, artillery, anti-tank and air defence and communication systems: the aim being to create a secure, integrated, efficient and cost-effective Army.

The Army headquarters is located at Grootfontein Military Base, a former SANDF logistics base. The Namibian Army is a hierarchical organisation with the Army commander exercising overall command and it trains along the lines of other Commonwealth armies. As such, the standard operational units are structured according to the British Commonwealth system presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Structure of the NDF

Type of Unit	Contains		Personnel	Commanded by
Division	2 – 3	Brigades	10,000	Maj-General
Brigade	3 – 5	Battalions	5,000	Brig-General
Battalion/regiment	5 – 7	Companies	550 - 900	Lt Colonel
Company/squadron	3	Platoons	120	Major
Platoon/troop	3	Sections	30	Captain, Lt, or 2nd Lt
Section	2	Fire teams	8–10	Corporal
Fire team	4	Individuals	4	Lance Corporal

Source: MOD, 2005

Table 1 illustrates the makeup of the existing NDF units. These units are spread across the nation and consist of an Air Defence Brigade, artillery units, and infantry units (such as the 21 Brigade), as well as motorised infantry brigades, the Engineering Regiment, the Logistics Support Battalion, the Military Police Battalion, the Signal Regiment, and various training units. Among the training units is the Army Technical Training Centre (TTC), which instructs army personnel in mechanics and electrical systems for armaments, military weapons, and equipment. Conversely, the School of Artillery oversees all soldiers who aspire to become artillery gunners.

II.II. THE NAMIBIAN AIR FORCE

The MoD's policy for the Air Force is as follows:

To acquire dedicated air assets to undertake the surveillance and transport tasks. The MOD and NDF will train and employ their own pilots and technicians. Co-operation and co-ordination with other Ministries may extend to making such assets available for non-defence tasking. In addition, consideration will be given to arrangements whereby private and other national air assets could be employed where appropriate or necessary (MOD, 2005).

The Namibian Air Force comprises several units, including an Air Defence Wing, 15 Wing, 13 Wing, a School of Air Power Studies, and the Air Force Technical Training Centre (TTC). The Technical Training Centre is responsible for providing technical

education to the ground personnel of the Air Force, with its curriculum developed in collaboration with the Namibian Aviation Training Academy. The qualifications available encompass certificates and diplomas in Mechanics, Avionics, and Armament (MOD, 2005).

II.III. THE NAMIBIAN NAVY

The Ministry of Defence stipulates the naval policy as:

In peacetime, the Namibian Navy has a role of augmenting civil offshore patrol forces, particularly providing the means and the expertise to execute enforcement action effectively. Specific tasks include assisting civil forces to combat illegal immigration, smuggling (arms, drugs etc.) and threats to the environment; conducting maritime surveillance, search and rescue; and assisting the Ministry of Fisheries with the enforcement of a fisheries protection regime. A longer-term peacetime task is the protection of offshore oil, gas, diamonds and other installations. A navy aerial surveillance component is a necessary part of the defence system (MOD, 2005).

The Navy is a hierarchical organisation with the navy commander exercising overall command. The Navy has 1,000 personnel, mostly trained in Brazil and South Africa. The Navy is further augmented by the Namibian Marine Corps (MOD, 2005); at full strength, the Namibian Marine Corps is a battalion unit of the Navy and its role is to provide naval infantry, amphibious, diving and small-boat capability to the Navy.

II.IV. THE NAMIBIAN MILITARY SCHOOL

The Namibian Military School at Osona Base is the primary training institution of the NDF and provides basic training for all NDF recruits. The basic training for recruits is six months long, and is offered in two phases; basic military training and platoon weapons training. Drills, field craft, skill at weapons, minor strategy, counter-insurgency operations, military hygiene, military law, first aid, map reading, and law of armed conflict and conventional warfare are only a few of the military topics covered. The Officer Cadet Course is also available at the academy.

As of 2013, the University of Namibia and the School of Military Science jointly began offering the undergraduate Bachelor of Military Science (Honours) degree, with three specialisation areas: Aeronautical, Army, and Nautical. The Nautical specialisation is sub-divided into a further three fields, namely: Nautical-Electronics, Nautical Mechanical, and Nautical Weapon Systems.

In November 2017 the NDF announced that the criteria for recruitment would change, to ensure that all recruits who join the NDF would have to first obtain a Bachelor's degree. The first intake for the Bachelor of Military Science (Honours) degree was in 2014 and the first- and second-group graduates completed their qualifications in 2018 and 2019 respectively. Subsequently, all Military Science graduates are recruited in the NDF.

The University of Namibia (UNAM) in conjunction with the Military School also offers a postgraduate Diploma in Security and Strategic Studies and a Master of Arts in Security and Strategic Studies (MA-SSS). The MA-SSS programme was the first to be implemented as a joint curriculum between UNAM and the Ministry of Defence, in 2007 and it mainly enrolls SCOs of the Namibian military. In 2012, the postgraduate Diploma in Security and Strategic Studies was also initiated by the Ministry of Defence and UNAM as a bridging course to help students prepare for the tougher MA-SSS course.

II.V. THE NDF COMMISSIONED OFFICER RANK

The Chief of the NDF, in terms of the Defence Act, appoints members of the Namibian Defence Force (Act 1 of 2002). The members of the NDF are divided into officers, warrant officers and other ranks. An officer is defined as a member to whom a commission has been conferred under section 21 of the Defence Act, 2002 (Act 1 of 2002). Officers are grouped into JCOs, SCOs, and General Officers. The various ranks of the three arms of services of the NDF are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. NDF rank and grading system

Grade		Rank			Functional level	Post level
		Army	Air Force	Navy		
Junior	Grade 12	Officer Cadet	Officer Cadet	Midshipman	Under training	-
	Grade 10	2nd Lieutenant	2nd Lieutenant	Ensign	Operational	Entry post
	Grade 9	Lieutenant	Lieutenant	Lieutenant Junior Grade (N)	Supervisory	1st promotion
	Grade 8	Captain	Captain	Lieutenant (N)	Supervisory	2nd promotion
SCOs	Grade 7	Major	Major	Lieutenant Commander	Overhead supervisory	3rd promotion
	Grade 6	Lieutenant Colonel	Lieutenant Colonel	Commander	Overhead supervisory	4th promotion
	Grade 4	Colonel	Colonel	Captain (N)	Professional management	5th promotion
General	Grade 3	Brigadier General	Brigadier General	Commodore	Professional management	6th promotion
	Grade 2	Major General	Major General	Rear Admiral	General management	7th promotion
	-	Chief of the Defence Force				

Source: MOD (2005)

Table 2 shows that the NDF does not specifically provide a post for officer cadets. Those involved are carried out-of-adjustment against vacant posts of 2nd Lieutenant or Ensign. If this arrangement results in significant numbers of officer cadets failing to be employed (due to the lack of vacancies), the Chief of the Defence Force is approached for the additional employment of incumbents on these levels.

The officer cadet cohort, as under-training interns, includes personnel who undergo formal and informal occupational-specific training and perform tasks resulting from different knowledge acquired during training under the supervision of a supervisor. The in-service training is offered through the Military School and affiliated training institutions locally and internationally. This provides an opportunity for the NDF to create a reserve force of officer cadets that can undertake studies in tertiary and vocational institutions. For instance, in the USA, military schools offer free tuition for military-related tertiary education, on condition that when they graduate the students will serve in the military. These strategies help to ensure that the military has a large pool of skilled reserve JCOs who can be called upon to serve at appropriate times.

II.VI. THE ROLE OF JUNIOR COMMISSIONED OFFICERS

JCOs in the NDF are mainly responsible for operational and supervisory functions. JCOs independently perform activities and supervise support staff where necessary. They also supervise occupationally related operational staff and if necessary, overhead supervision of supporting staff. As such, officers of all arms and services need to be motivated to acquire education in multi-disciplinary subjects relevant to the profession of arms, like Management, Information Technology (IT), Behavioural Sciences, and Military History. This will widen their horizons and facilitate the development of the multi-disciplinary outlook. Without education, personnel would be a more of a liability rather than an asset on the battlefield. Educating officers is imperative to ensure that personnel are able to operate confidently on the modern technology-dominated battlefield.

The NDF is facing numerous challenges in its endeavour to impart high-quality education through its training programmes. The socio-economic transformation of the Namibian society; the technological changes coupled with problems of technology assimilation; and shrinking defence budgets and fiscal constraints are only some of the issues.

Training seeks to improve and develop the knowledge, skills, and/or attitudes of soldiers. Apart from the benefits accruing to the individual member, many advantages accrue to the organisation too. In the past, semi-educated soldiers were able to meet the demands of their employment, but that is no longer the case. The twenty-first century soldier needs to understand and analyse situations as they unfold, especially in times of conflict since the modern battlefield requires soldiers to be creative, innovative, knowledgeable, and mentally resourceful in order to meet rapidly changing and fluid tactical situations.

II.VII. MODELS OF MILITARY TALENT MANAGEMENT

Global armed forces are increasingly facing difficulties in attracting, enlisting, and retaining the required numbers of new recruits (Alvinius, Johansson, & Larsson, 2017). The recruiting and retention problem can be linked to a variety of causes, including: the situation on the labour market, the conflict between military values and prevailing values in society, the content of the military

job (e.g., wages, promotion system, geographical mobility) and the management of the major processes of recruitment, selection and classification, turnover, and retention (Alvinus et al., 2017).

III. MILITARY RECRUITMENT

The difficulty in recruiting sufficient numbers in the military is aggravated by a military culture that is necessarily steeped in discipline and obedience and that is in contrast with demands for greater individualisation and participation in decision-making among youths (Heinecken, 2009). Moreover, many military personnel attrite prior to the completion of their initial contracts. While attrition rates are country- and time- dependent, it is usual that 30 per cent or more of enlisted recruits do not complete their first term (NATO, 2007). In addition, military personnel in specialised fields who are expensive to recruit and train – such as pilots, engineers, and communication experts – can choose to return to civilian life later in their careers, attracted by more appealing private sector opportunities.

Despite these challenges, militaries can be slow in bringing their service conditions in line with the private sector in terms of employment conditions, salaries, and management styles. A military career is also known for placing high demands on the individual and family life. Conflict between the military and family arises due to the demands made upon personnel in terms of the risk of death, geographic mobility, family separation, residence in foreign countries, and constraints on spouses and children (Segal, 1986).

Huibers (2011) studied how employer attraction and retention practices have changed, or need to change, in response to generational changes in the workplace. The study identified four generations in the work place, namely: The Traditionalists, the Baby Boomers, Generation X, and Generation Y (Huibers, 2011). The study assessed strategies employers are incorporating in attracting and retaining the current youth demography, termed the Generation Y. This generation is sometimes referred to as the ‘millennial generation’ or the ‘net generation’, because of the influence of the rapid evolution of digital technology which characterises them.

Understanding Generation Y is critical to the effectiveness of NDF recruitment and retention strategies aimed at those born between 1980 and 2000 since this cohort represents the typical JCO in the NDF, as well as the pool of professionals the NDF will need to replace its aging and retiring SCOs. Sujansky and Ferri-Reed (2009) argue that the millennials (born after the year 2000) will bring in new styles and perspectives in organisations, therefore, organisations should be willing to adapt or risk losing millions of dollars to unwanted turnover and lost productivity. Since this generation is well educated, skilled in technology, and very self-confident (Huybers, 2011) they tend to have a high degree of accomplishment and even higher expectations. They also prefer constant feedback and detailed instructions, factors that make them more at ease in the workplace and able to do the job properly.

Bartley et al. (2007) argue that this generation expects to see some sort of structure, can multitask, can acknowledge authority, and wants a professional relationship with their boss. As most military organisations are well structured, this has positive connotations for recruiting among the millennial generation. However, that structure must be fair and provide a strong basis for organisational justice, which is a critical element in the expectations of the millennials. Gould-Williams and Davies (2007) argue that through social exchange relationships, people form expectations of others’ competence based on status and the expectations they have about other people’s professional roles. The military structure should therefore support these expectations. However, inconsistencies in NDF policy and practices in areas such as promotion opportunities, working conditions, and special benefits immensely affect the attractiveness of the military structure to millennial JCOs.

This generation of millennial JCOs is prone to changing jobs swiftly if they perceive injustices in the workplace or become bored with their job for long periods; they must be continuously engaged and challenged in order to excel (Huibers, 2011). This is unlike the older generation of military personnel, whose members have mostly reached retirement age.

Furthermore, the younger generation have a different outlook on their work-life balance (Huybers, 2011). For millennials, work-life balance means more than just working for a salary as they are looking to achieve a certain lifestyle, with specific personal goals and priorities (Sujansky & Ferri-Reed, 2009). It is noted that since a high salary is not at the top of their list of goals, this generation is more interested in social exchanges within the organisational culture and interactions with direct supervisors and military leadership (Huibers, 2011).

This is supported by Theodore’s (2003) study on the trends and factors influencing recruitment and retention. This study highlights the factors that influence the quality and readiness of the future US defence forces. These factors include demographics, education, organisational leadership, job satisfaction, compensation benefits, quality of life, and propensity to serve. Moreover, the factors represent different aspects of the social exchange that include the specific procedures involved (HRM practices); the nature (recruitment or turnover), character or spirit of the exchange (positive or negative); or the tangible and intangible outcomes of the exchange (commitment or loyalty) (Theodore, 2003).

III.I. MODEL OF MILITARY RECRUITMENT

Schreurs and Syed (2007) propose a behavioural prediction model of military recruitment that is based on a behavioural variable of job pursuit.

Figure 1 presents Schreurs and Syed’s (2007) model of military recruitment based on a review of recruitment research conducted on both military and non-military samples, and on the efforts of members of the NATO Task Group on Recruitment and Retention of Military Personnel (NATO, 2007). These two scholars argue that job-pursuit can take many forms (such as applying or job offer acceptance) that depend on the recruitment stage of the applicant. The model is in line with other models of behavioural prediction, like Ajzen and Fishbein (1977)’s theory of reasoned action and Ajzen (1991)’s theory of planned behaviour.

Figure 1: Model of military recruitment

Source: Schreurs and Syed (2007)

This model of military recruitment assumes that a person’s intention to act is the immediate antecedent of behaviour and that intention can be predicted by the extent to which a person has a positive or negative attitude toward the behaviour (Schreurs and Syed, 2007). Be that as it may, the model consists of organisational-level and individual-level predictor variables, and outcome variables. In terms of salary levels and organisational size characteristics; the individual level predictor variables refer to the perceived environment with regards to individuals’ subjective interpretation of the job and organisational characteristics such as imagination or familiarity (Schreurs & Syed, 2007).

The model of military recruitment shown in

Figure 1 includes a variety of determinant predictors of applicant attraction such as the individual’s cognitions (beliefs, perceptions, expectations) that are expected to influence attitude and/or intention. Moreover, the model relies on principles from Shannon and Weaver (1949)’s information and communication theory (cited in Ritchie, 1986) to contextualise the transmission

of the recruitment message to the target group of potential applicants. For the NDF, the message of recruitment should now be reflected in the millennial generation through suitable mediums.

The message content includes information on the available jobs, the type of work to be performed, the pay level(s), and the organisational factors that play a critical role in the individual's decision-making process. The principles from information and communication theory were relied on to describe how information about the organisation is communicated through various information sources to the target population. The model makes a distinction between sources that are under the direct control of the organisation (like advertisements) and external sources beyond the organisation (such as word-of-mouth) (Schreurs & Syed, 2007).

The African Security Review (2014) study on South Africa's high school scholars' view of military service looked at the factors affecting the ability of the South African National Defence Force (SANDF) to attract suitable recruits to staff its modern, technologically advanced military (Smith & Heineken, 2014). The study noted that despite the high levels of youth unemployment in South Africa, which would naturally mean a sufficient recruitment pool for military service recruits, the SANDF fails to recruit sufficient high-quality personnel with the right profile and abilities.

The identified causal factors support the model of military recruitment, which highlights a growing knowledge gap and disconnect between the military and South African society due to factors such as external information sources that can cause gender- and or race groups 'estrangement' (Smith & Heineken, 2014). For instance, perceptions of masculinity in the military can push away female recruits. Smith and Heineken (2014) also note the need to address these aspects in a way that influences the attitudes and job-pursuit intentions of learners with good academic credentials, as these individual-level influences will improve the quality of future military recruits. On the other hand, Schreurs and Syed (2007) highlight organisational-level factors that affect military recruitment, such as poor service conditions, a decline in the prestige of the military, and certain unfavourable aspects associated with the military culture.

III.II. MODEL OF MILITARY RETENTION

Retention researchers have defined retention management as a strategic, coherent process that starts with an examination of the reasons why employees join an organisation (NATO, 2007). A number of different factors can affect employee turnover and, in many countries, the military is facing a serious loss of (often highly qualified) personnel who are resigning for a number of reasons. It can be the case that one event may act as a catalyst for the employee to leave but the underlying reasons are attributable to multiple events during the employee's time in the military. A NATO (2007) research noted a variety of factors including incongruence between prevailing social values and the military organisational culture; military operational and promotions systems based on seniority versus merit; and a mismatch between individual interests and job assignments (NATO, 2007).

With today's competitive job market, employee retention is an important issue for most organisations. Job opportunities exist for skilled and talented employees, who are also quick to look elsewhere if they are dissatisfied with their current job. This is putting pressure on the military system – which is failing to implement retention policies and practices and must deal with aging military personnel – which needs to foster an environment that encourages current employees to remain employed for a maximum period.

Capon et al. (2007) assessed the applicability of the civilian retention theory to the military by exploring the relationship between established determinants of retention and intentions to remain in the New Zealand Army. They used hypotheses based on the civilian theory to form the basis of a preliminary military retention model. They then tested this model on 97 individuals who were enlisted in the Army using regression and path modelling. They modelled work satisfaction and organisational commitment as proximal predictors of intentions to remain in the military (Capon et al., 2007). They found that these predictors mediate the relationship between more distal predictors and retention. The results signified the relevance and usefulness of civilian research in predicting retention in the military. Figure 1 presents the resultant model of military retention.

Capon et al. (2007) argue that in civilian research; retention is treated as an instance of motivated personal choice, which is largely influenced by one's dispositions, attitudes and feelings. On the other hand, military retention research focuses primarily on the relationships between personnel demographics and organisational characteristics and enlistment of outcomes such as retention. In the military, little emphasis is placed on the possible contributions of affective predictors and personality traits in other words. As such, their study attempted to integrate the two bodies of research, and Figure 1 presents the integrated retention

model applicable to military retention. This model is consistent with predictions that work satisfactorily, such as community identification and organisational commitment as the leading predictors of intentions to remain in the military (Capon et al., 2007).

The study noted that work satisfaction and organisational commitment fully mediates the relationship between other predictors of intentions to remain, such as dispositions, job involvement, perceived organisational support, and met expectations. Nonetheless, the study also found contradictory evidence to previous civilian findings concerning the levels of satisfaction of individuals experiencing work-family conflict.

These findings are reasonable for the older military generation, which has increasingly accepted the work-family conflict drawback of a military career. The practical implications of these findings offer an opportunity for creating realistic expectations about a military career or providing consistent levels of organisational support, as a way of increasing retention in the army in the future (Capon et al., 2007).

Figure 2: Model of military retention

Source: Capon et al. (2007)

A similar military model research by Gencer (2002) focused on factors influencing the retention intentions of junior male officers in the US Army. The study found that JCOs' decisions to remain on active duty were significantly influenced by distal predictors such as military rank, expectations of military life, satisfaction with military intrinsic values, military career-advancement opportunities, as well as military deployment and economic life. The proximal predictors such as the probability of finding a good civilian job cannot be ignored as well.

Gencer (2002) used logistic regression quadrant analysis to determine that workload, personal time, and enjoyment satisfaction had a considerable impact on overall satisfaction with military life and had substantial room for improvement. The influence of distal predictors was assumed to be mediated fully by proximal predictors. For instance, job involvement is a proximal predictor, which mediates the distal predictor variable, work-family conflict (Capon et al., 2007).

A more recent study by Vasterling et al. (2015) on the predictors of military retention in enlisted US Army soldiers 12 months after deployment to Iraq, supports the Capon *et al.* (2007) model. The study concluded that service members early in their career (with less than six years of service) were especially prone to military attrition, which implies that it takes nearly six years for service members to firmly establish a commitment to a military career (Vasterling, et al., 2015).

Vasterling et al. (2015) reported that military retention was influenced by multiple individual and environmental factors and their findings also suggest the importance of developing initiatives that target organisational cohesion and support. Moreover, during and after a war-zone deployment, the instrumental and emotional support provided by peers and military leaders was found to be one of the most important retention factors (Vasterling, et al., 2015).

III.III. THE TURNOVER MODEL

Hom et al. (2012) reconceptualised employee turnover to understand and predict the reasons why employees quit or stay in employing institutions. They proposed a proximal withdrawal status framework which looks at factors that motivate members to participate or withdraw from organisations.

Figure 3: Proximal motivational states framework

Source: Adapted from Hom et al. (2012).

Table 3: Interpretation of the proximal motivational states to participate or withdraw

Withdrawal states and subtypes	Immediate antecedents	Consequent attitudes and behaviours	Time to leave	Turnover destinations
Enthusiastic stayers				
Engaged stayers	High affective, calculative, or constituent force	Good performance, OCBs, less CWBs and WABs; positive JS and OC	Slow	Retirement destinations, disability (disease, injury, infirmity), death, or unsolicited job offer
Embedded engaged stayers	High affective, calculative, or constituent force and high sacrifices or normative	Same as engaged stayers	Slower than engaged stayers	Retirement destinations, disability, death, or unsolicited job offer

	forces to stay			
Slackers	NS job over fit or DA job fit (but low D and A) and high job /community sacrifice or low alternative force (no better jobs)	Poor performance, less OCBs and WABs; average JS and OC	Slow	Retirement destinations, disability, death, or no options (due to dismissal or layoff)
Reluctant stayers				
Trapped stayers	Low affective, calculative, or constituent force and high normative force to stay, high sacrifices, or low alternative force (no jobs)	Marginal performance, WABs, CWBs, less OCBs, job search; negative JS and OC	Moderate (removal of exit barriers)	Another job, unpaid work (e.g., full-time caretaker), or no work option (e.g., MBA enrolment)
Contractual stayers	Low affective or calculative force and high legal force (employment contract)	Minimally acceptable performance, less OCBs, little CWBs or WABs; somewhat negative JS and OC	Moderate (contract duration)	Another job, unpaid work, no work, or no option
Enthusiastic leavers (voluntary leaving subclasses)				
Path 1 (plan)	High alternative force	Adequate to good performance, OCBs, less CWBs or WABs, continued positive JS and OC	Implement plan soon after shock	Retirement destinations, unpaid work, no work, or no option
Path 2 (negative job shock)	Low affective (image violation) or constituent (bullies, bad bosses) force	Poor performance, CWBs; negative JS and OC	Very quickly, just quits	No option
Path 3 (job offer)	High alternative force (unsolicited job inquiry or offer)	Adequate to good performance, OCBs, less CWBs or WABs, continued positive JS and OC	Moderate	Another (zer) job
Path 4 (dissatisfaction) Reluctant leavers	Low affective (initial negative JS and OC), calculative, or constituent force All subtypes below should have high affective, calculative, or constituent force to stay and a force (or forces) to leave	Poor performance, WABs, job search, less OCBs, CWBs; more negative JS and OC	Slower	Another job
Involuntary leavers	High legal force to leave (suspected or anticipated terminations)	Poor performance (or attempts to upgrade performance), WABs, job search; increasingly negative JS and OC	Faster to quick	No option (or another job if lined up before leaving) or poor options
Traditional retiring leavers	High legal force to leave and moderate to high alternative forces (pension eligibility, early retirement incentives)	Moderate to good performance, OCBs, little CWBs or WABs; above average JS and OC	Slower	Bridge employment, unpaid work (e.g., volunteer), no work, or no option
Coerced leavers	High normative force to leave (e.g., pressing family care duties, spousal	Moderate to good performance, OCBs, little CWBs or WABs; likely	Moderate to slow	Another job, unpaid work, or no work option (less desirable options)

	relocations, family dislocations)	positive JS and OC		
Resistant leavers	High legal force to leave and high normative pressure to stay, high sacrifice, or lack of desirable jobs	Resistance, poor performance (or attempts to upgrade performance), WABs, job search; increasingly negative JS and OC	Moderate to slow	No option (or another job lined up before leaving); possible reinstatement.

Note. OCBs = organisational citizenship behaviours; CWBs = counterproductive work behaviours; WABs = work avoidance behaviours (e.g., absences, tardiness); JS = job satisfaction; OC = affective organisational commitment; NS = needs-supplies; DA = demands-abilities; D = demands; A = abilities.

Source: Adapted from Hom et al. (2012).

The proximal motivational states to participate or withdraw configurations (Figure) and interpretations on Table 3: **Interpretation of the proximal motivational states to participate or withdraw** provide practical implications for recruitment and retention research in the military. As such, they provide a framework or configuration that personnel managers in the military can use as a tool for diagnosing the prevalent mind-sets of service members. The configurations for staying or leaving provide greater clarification regarding the mind-sets of the members prior to their decision to leave the army. Thus, identifying these correct withdrawal states can assist personnel managers in coming up with strategies that can help organisations target and manage different mind-sets with appropriate retention policies (Rousseau, Ho, & Greenberg, 2006).

Bothma and Roodt (2013) notes that leaving a job might not always be an option for an individual; Hom et al. (2012) framework accurately highlights how the decision to leave (proximal withdrawal state) is influenced by many personal (employee preference) and contextual factors such as employability (employer control) and labour market conditions (other extrinsic control). An individual's turnover intention is dependent on other extrinsic control aspects such as the perceived chances and ease of finding another job (especially in tough economic conditions); the role of mobility cognitions; and individual differences in search behaviour (Bothma & Roodt, 2013). Therefore, turnover destinations (such as alternative employment opportunities) influence actual labour turnover behaviour.

Bothma (2011) found that the turnover phenomenon has significant costs and other negative implications for any organisation. These include losing highly skilled employees, resulting in the disruption of organisations through impaired organisational functioning, service delivery, and administration. In support, Haimbala (2014) notes that the level of resignations among newly recruited and qualified NDF personnel was of concern and questions concerning the older soldiers' future has become complicated with the exit of those inherited from PLAN and SWATF, who at this stage are no longer active participants in combat and peacekeeping missions.

The negative attitude towards the employing organisation – including a belief that the organisation lacks integrity, and that the principles of fairness, honesty, and sincerity are sacrificed in favour of organisational interests – is defined as 'organisational cynicism' (Goldenberg, Kocum, & Laplante, 2017). Goldenberg et al. (2017) notes that organisational cynicism is developed through repeated exposure to negative organisational experiences and ineffective attempts at organisational change. Furthermore, they argue that cynicism is unrelated to the trait of negative affectivity. In their study on the extent to which perceptions of organisational justice relate to work and organisational cynicism, Goldenberg et al. (2017) found that about commitment, cynicism mediates the effect of justice perceptions on commitment. They further indicated that greater cynicism is related to decreased commitment, lower job satisfaction, lower intentions to perform organisational-citizenship behaviours, and increased intentions to comply with requests to engage in unethical behaviours.

III.IV. MODEL OF MILITARY TURNOVER

Sümer and van de Ven (2007) propose a model of military turnover that treats voluntary turnover as a product of an individual's subjective experience of the job and the organisation, which exists within the broader social, economic, and cultural milieu. Figure 2 presents the model of military turnover.

Figure 2: Model of military turnover

Source: Sümer and van de Ven (2007).

This model considers the potential impact of both macro-level labour market parameters and a micro-level, decision-making approach that explains the military turnover process. The model uses an individual-centred approach that treats turnover as a more manageable and predictable phenomenon by the organisation through the coordination of critical HRM activities such as recruitment, selection, classification, and continuous monitoring (Sümer & van de Ven, 2007).

The model in Figure 2 focuses mainly on the psychological processes and the individual’s subjective experiences, as it recognises the unemployment rate as a critical determinant of military turnover. As such, the model establishes a link between the micro-level, individual-focused psychological approach and a macro-level, labour market-focused economic approach. The model aims to account for turnover that is not necessarily attitude-based (Sümer & van de Ven, 2007). One major implication of this model is that military organisations should routinely monitor employee attitudes – mainly satisfaction and commitment, and factors contributing to the development of these attitudes. This model also allows for the possibility that turnover may not result from dissatisfaction or lack of commitment but rather from macro-level external factors, such as the rate of unemployment, and/or unexpected life events.

III.V. DEVELOPMENT OF A MODEL FOR THE RETENTION OF JCOs IN THE NDF

The final research management framework was presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** on the next page and provides the NDF recruitment officers with an interpersonal pathway for managing the recruitment, promotion and retention of JCOs in the NDF towards reducing the high turnover rates of JCOs. The proposed model focuses on the job-pursuit intentions of JCOs, which are positively influenced by gender, military rank, military unit and location of the unit. Accordingly, the recruitment officers using this management framework will rely on the individual JCO’s perceptions of organisational justice – particularly, procedural and distributive justice. The management implications for this framework are based on how fair HRM practices are perceived within the NDF and this

Fig 5: Management model for retention of JCOs in the Namibian Defence Force

IV. CONCLUSION

The study highlighted the impact of recruitment and retention practices on military performance through international case studies and discussed the various recruitment and retention strategies and their influence on performance. The proposed talent management model should be continuously updated to focus on the younger generation JCOs, who have an evolving outlook on what their work-life balance means. In support, Sujansky and Ferri-Reed (2009) argues that work-life balance is more than pay and benefits, but also looks at factors such community involvement that is meant to achieve a certain lifestyle, with specific personal goals and priorities. The study argues that goals and priorities are influenced by marital status and military rank of the JCOs was. Since a high salary is not at the top of their list of goals, this generation is more interested in social exchanges within the organisational culture and interactions with direct supervisors and military leadership (Huibers, 2011).

REFERENCES

1. Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behaviour. *Organisational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*, 50, 179-211.
2. Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (1977). Attitude-behaviour relations: A theoretical analysis and review of empirical research. *Psychological bulletin*, 84(5), 88.
3. Alvinus, A., Johansson, E., & Larsson, G. (2017). Job satisfaction as a form of organisational commitment at the military strategic level A grounded theory study. *International Journal of Organisational Analysis*, 25(2).
4. Bartley, S., Ladd, P., & Morris, M. (2007). Managing the multigenerational workplace: Answers for managers and trainers. *CUPA-HR Journal*, 28-34.
5. Bothma, C. F., & Roodt, G. (2013). The validation of the turnover intention scale. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 11(1).
6. Capon, J., Chernyshenko, O., & Stark, S. (2007, March). Applicability of Civilian Retention Theory in the New Zealand Military. *New Zealand Journal of Psychology*, 36(1).
7. Gencer, U. (2002). An analysis of factors affecting the retention plans of junior male U.S. Army Officers: evidence from the 1999 DOD Survey of active duty personnel. *PHD Thesis*. Monterey, California: Naval Postgraduate School.
8. Goldenberg, I., Kocum, L., & Laplante, J. (2017, July). Uncommitted to the Unfair : The Mediating Role of Work and Organisational Cynicism. *Res Militaris, ERGOMAS*, 4.
9. Gould-Williams, J., & Davies, F. (2007). Using social exchange theory to predict the effects of HRM practice on employee outcomes An analysis of public sector workers Julian Gould-Williams & Fiona Davies Pages 1-24.

10. Haimbala, A. N. (2014, April). An Investigative Study on the Namibian Defence Force's Combat Readiness Focusing on Alternative Policy of Termination and Retention of Expertise in the Military Services . *Msc. Thesis*. Windhoek: UNAM.
11. Heinecken, L. (2009). Discontent within the ranks? Officers' attitudes toward military employment and representation: a four country comparative study. *Armed Forces and Society*, 35, 477–500.
12. Hom, P. W., Mitchell, T. R., Lee, T. W., & Griffith, R. W. (2012). Reviewing Employee Turnover:Focusing on Proximal Withdrawal States and an Expanded Criterion. *Psychological Bulletin*, 138(5), 831–858.
13. Huybers, C. (2011, May). The Recruitment and Retention of Generation Y. *MSc Thesis*. Graduate School, University of Wisconsin-Stout.
14. MoD. (2005, October 27). No. 138 General regulations relating to Namibian Defence Force. *Government Gazette of the Republic of Namibia*, No. 3525. Retrieved from <https://gazettes.africa/archive/na/2005/na-government-gazette-dated-2005-10-27-no-3525.pdf>
15. MoD. (2007). *A report on the Ministry of Defence's Strategic Workshop*. Windhoek: Ministry of Defence.
16. NATO. (2007, October). Recruiting and Retention of Military Personnel. *NATO RTO Technical Report: Final Report of Research Task Group HFM-107*. Brussels: Research and Technology Organisation & North Atlantic Treaty Organisation.
17. NDF. (2008). *Annual Report*. Windhoek: Namibia Defence Force.
18. NDF. (2016). *Annual Report 2015*. Windhoek: Ministry of Defence-Namibia Defence Force.
19. NDF. (2016). *Namibian Defence Force (NDF) Annual Report*. Windhoek: Ministry of Defence-Namibian Defence Force.
20. NDF CDP. (2004). *The Career Development Plan of the NDF*. Windhoek: Ministry of Defence-Namibia Defence Force.
21. NDF OPS. (1995). *NDF Operational Training Doctrine/Training for War* . Windhoek: Ministry of Defence - Namibia Defence Force.
22. Ritchie, D. (1986). Shannon and Weaver: Unravelling the paradox of information. *Communication research*, 13(2), 278-298.
23. Rousseau, D. H., & Greenberg, J. (2006). I-deals: Idiosyncratic terms in employment relationships. *Academy of Management Review*, 977–994.
24. Schreurs, B., & Syed, F. (2007). A Proposed Model of Military Recruitment . In NATO, *RTO Technical Report TR-HFM-107:Recruiting and Retention of Military Personnel* (pp. 299-324). Brussels: Research and Technology Organisation & North Atlantic Treaty Organisation.
25. Smith, M., & Heinecken, L. (2014). Factors influencing military recruitment in South Africa: the voices of Cape Town high school learners. *African Security Review*, 23(2), 102-116.
26. Sujansky, J., & Ferri-Reed, J. (2009). *Keeping the millennials: Why companies are losing billions in turnover to this generation-and what to do about it*. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons.
27. Sümer, C., & van de Ven, C. (2007). A Proposed Model of Military Turnover. In NATO, *RTO TECHNICAL REPORT TR-HFM-107:Recruiting and Retention of Military Personnel* (pp. 324-343). Brussels: RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY ORGANISATION & NORTH ATLANTIC TREATY ORGANISATION.
28. Theodore, D. E. (2003, April 7). Recruiting and Retention, A Force Planning Dilemma, USA. *USAWC Strategy Research Project*. US Army War College.
29. Vasterling, J. j., Proctor, s. p., Aslan, M., Ko, J., Jakupcak, M., Harte, C. B., . . . Concato, J. (2015). Military, demographic, and psychosocial predictors of military retention in enlisted army soldiers 12 months after deployment. *Military Medicine*, 180(5), 524.